

Day 2. Thursday, 9 October 2025

14:00 - 18:00 CEST, online

14:00 - 14:30	<p>A recap of day 1 and outline of day 2 Katrina Exter (VLIZ) How to use the Miro boards today Emilie Boulanger (UNESCO)</p>
14:30 - 15:30	<p>Breakout Sessions A Data publishers (DNA and biodiversity) Katrina Exter (VLIZ) and Christina Pavloudi (EMBRC) B Reference libraries, Bioinformatics, Taxonomies (data) Emilie Boulanger and Saara Suominen (UNESCO) C Biobanks, Culture collections, Taxonomies (concepts) Pascal Hablutzel (VLIZ) and Tom Collart (Seascape Belgium) Attendees can select their own groups Attendees can take breaks as and when they wish during the session</p>
15:30 - 16:00	<p>Plenary: summary of the breakouts / Break</p>
16:00 - 17:00	<p>Breakout Sessions A Data publishers (DNA and biodiversity) Katrina Exter (VLIZ) and Christina Pavloudi (EMBRC) B Reference libraries, Bioinformatics, Taxonomies (data) Emilie Boulanger and Saara Suominen (UNESCO) C Biobanks, Culture collections, Taxonomies (concepts) Pascal Hablutzel (VLIZ) and Tom Collart (Seascape Belgium) Attendees can return to the previous group or select a new one Attendees can take breaks as and when they wish during the session</p>
17:00 - 17:30	<p>Plenary: summary of the breakouts. Workshop debrief and next steps</p>

<https://tinyurl.com/bdd7rvef>

Breakout session A: DNA and biodiversity data publishers

Blueprint for a future eDNA data ecosystem

Breakout group A: *DNA and biodiversity data publishers*

Day 2. 14:30-15:45 16:15-17:30

14:00 -14:30	Plenary: summary and intro to the sessions
14:30 - 15:30	Miro board work. Getting your feedback on specific points in the Landscaping report. Pre-workshop reading material can be found in the public folder for the workshop (https://tinyurl.com/56rxpccj), specifically in "README" and "Day 2: landscaping recommendations and discussion points". Coffee/health break can be freely taken during this session.
15:30 - 16:00	Plenary: summary of the breakouts / Break
16:00 - 17:00	Continuation of Miro board work. Continuation of the first session
17:00 - 17:30	Plenary: summary of the breakouts. Workshop debrief and next steps

Breakout session A: DNA and biodiversity data publishers

- Participants: data creators & data infrastructures/repositories Discuss the findings of our Landscaping report
 - Recommendations for improving provision, formatting, and treatment of metadata
 - Recommendations on data formatting and machine-understandability/accessibility
 - Cooperation on setting and sharing standards
 - Dealing with eDNA-based results in (not-only-omics) biodiversity archives, tools for submitting data, mapping between taxonomies
- Miro board with 4 question “Areas”; post-its for your feedback
 - Do you dis/agree?
 - What are the bottlenecks and the enablers?
 - Are these actions a priority for you?
 - Who should do it; and how to encourage doing it?

Breakout B: reference libraries, bioinformatics, taxonomic backbones (data)

eDNAqua-Plan <small>NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING</small>		Blueprint for a future eDNA data ecosystem	
Breakout group B: Reference libraries, Bioinformatics, Taxonomies (data)		Day 2. 14:30-15:45 16:15-17:30	
14:00 -14:30	Plenary: summary and intro to the sessions		
14:30 - 15:30	Miro board work. Getting your feedback on specific points in the Landscaping report. Pre-workshop reading material can be found in the public folder for the workshop (https://tinyurl.com/56rxpccj), specifically in "README" and "Day 2: landscaping recommendations and discussion points". Coffee/health break can be freely taken during this session.		
15:30 - 16:00	Plenary: summary of the breakouts / Break		
16:00 - 17:00	Continuation of Miro board work. Continuation of the first session		
17:00 - 17:30	Plenary: summary of the breakouts. Workshop debrief and next steps		

Breakout B: reference libraries, bioinformatics, taxonomic backbones (data)

- Participants: those who create, publish, or re-use reference libraries
- Discuss the vision for the system of interconnected and interoperable reference libraries
 - Federated network of quality-controlled reference libraries
 - Findable and reliable reference sequences
 - Essential set of metadata and common taxonomic curation principles
- Miro board with 3 question “Areas”; post-its for your feedback
 - Which aspects of the current landscape that work and do not work well do you dis/agree with and why?
 - Our vision of the future includes a federation of quality-controlled, taxonomically curated reference libraries. How could we make this a reality?
 - These reference libraries would be guided by a common set of essential metadata and curation principles. Do you agree with these?

Breakout C: Biobanks, culture collections, taxonomic backbones (concepts)

Blueprint for a future eDNA data ecosystem

Breakout group C: *Biobanks, Culture collections, Taxonomies (concepts)*

Day 2. 14:30-15:45 16:15-17:30

14:00 -14:30	Plenary: summary and intro to the sessions
14:30 - 15:30	Miro board-led discussion. Pre-workshop reading material can be found in the public folder for the workshop (https://tinyurl.com/56rxpccj), specifically in "README" and "Day 2: landscaping recommendations and discussion points".
15:30 - 16:00	Plenary: summary of the breakouts / Break
16:00 - 17:00	Miro board-led discussion. Continuation of the first session
17:00 - 17:30	Plenary: summary of the breakouts. Workshop debrief and next steps

Breakout C: Biobanks, culture collections, taxonomic backbones (concepts)

- Participants: those who curate biobanks and culture collections and identify/name samples, specimens or cultures
- Discuss the findings of our Landscaping report
 - Recommendations for continued digitalisation of biobanks and culture collections
 - Recommendations on data formatting and machine-understandability/accessibility
 - Cooperation on setting and sharing standards
 - Dealing with object that are difficult to name taxonomically
- Miro board with 4 question “Areas”; post-its for your feedback
 - Do you dis/agree?
 - What are the bottlenecks and the enablers?
 - Are these actions a priority for you?
 - Who should do it; and how to encourage doing it?

Introduction to our Miro boards

Miro boards are like e-chalkboards that allow for real-time collaboration.

We have created a board for each breakout session – 1,2,3 for day 1 and A, B for day 2

Each board has an area showing

- The future landscape
- The list of questions that we want to be addressed in the session, with a link to the reading material relevant for those questions
- An area for each question in which you will add your comments, thoughts, feedback as “post-its” aka “sticky notes”

The links to each Miro boards can be found in the README in our google drive

(<https://tinyurl.com/bdd7rvef>), the link to which was sent to you all over the weekend

Introduction to our DAY 2 Miro boards

ED eDNAqua-Plan
eDNAqua-Plan

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Quickly access your most important Spaces by pinning them.

Spaces

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miro

Blank board Blueprint Roadmap

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Filter by All boards Owned by anyone...

Name

- Day 1 - Breakout session 1
Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3
- Day 1 - Breakout session 2
Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3
- Day 1 - Breakout session 3
Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3
- Day 2 - Breakout session A
Modified by Peter Woollard, Oct 3
- Day 2 - Breakout session B
Modified by Emilie Boulanger, Yesterday
- Welcome Board | Starter Plan
Modified by Carlijn Koole, Sep 9
- Workshop Landing Board**
Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3

Introduction to our DAY 2 Miro boards

- ✓ Day 1 - Breakout session 2
Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3
- ✓ Day 1 - Breakout session 3
Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3
- 📅 Day 2 - Breakout session A
Modified by Peter Woollard, Oct 3
- 📅 Day 2 - Breakout session B
Modified by Emilie Boulanger, Yesterday
- 👤 Welcome Board | Starter Plan
Modified by Carlijn Koole, Sep 9
- 📍 Workshop Landing Board
Modified by Katrina Exter, Oct 3

Introduction to our DAY 2 Miro boards

Day 2 - Breakout session A

See <https://tinyurl.com/45udatad> for the summarised recommendations that are to be discussed in this session

Metadata Area: recommendations on discovery and provenance metadata. *Points 1-4*

Data formatting and machine-understandability Area: recommendations on data formats and making (meta)data machine-readable and understandable. *Points 5-7*

Cooperation and standards Area: recommendations on working together on standards. *Points 8-9*

Taxonomic- and bioinformatics-related issues Area: recommendations on dealing with these types of information in biodiversity data. *Points 10-12*

Metadata Area

See point 2 on <https://tinyurl.com/45udatad>

Checklists to indicate data are suitable for some purpose. See point 3 on <https://tinyurl.com/45udatad>

Do you agree or disagree? why?	Suggest benchmarks and enablers	Are these are priority for you?	Who is responsible for these recommendations?	How could we encourage this?	Any other type of comment
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Stronger requirements for providing provenance metadata. See point 4

Do you agree or disagree? why?	Suggest benchmarks and enablers	Are these are priority for you?	Who is responsible for these recommendations?	How could we encourage this?	Any other type of comment
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miro Day 1 - Breakout session 1

with the aspects of the current landscape and why?

Introduction to our DAY 2 Miro boards

Checklists to indicate data are suitable for some purpose. See point 3 on <https://tinyurl.com/45udatad>

- Do you agree or disagree? why?
- Suggest bottlenecks and enablers
- Are these are priority for you?
- Who is responsible for these recommendations?
- How could we encourage this?
- Any other type of comment

You can change rooms in the “Breakout rooms” icon (may be in “More” for narrow screens).

Now open the **README** in the w/s drive

<https://tinyurl.com/y6razjm7>

w/s folder: <https://tinyurl.com/bdd7rvef>

Thank you!

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A selected summary of Day 2

- **Provenance:** for more provenance metadata to be provided, we should provide templates and a provenance model.
- **Protocols:** recommendations on how to include these in metadata (as a DOI, as text, as a bit of both) should be issues
- We have to be **careful when making recommendations** for metadata and data: data infrastructures still do a lot of manual curation → so where to draw the line?
- The **FAIRe checklist** is definitely something we should work from when we make our recommendations and issue practical advice (e.g. templates and examples, tools, etc)
- Scientists/data creators are **overwhelmed when they submit data** with the requirements on the (meta)data. Use **e-notebooks/e-lab to collect from the beginning**, if those export the (meta)data for them, that would reduce the overwhelmingness. E-labs plug in the FAIRe checklist?

A selected summary of Day 2

- **More harmonisation** of the way MlxS (and look at DwC) are used by different data infrastructures: they are similar, but not exactly the same (written different, used different, examples different) and this is **confusing for the data submitters**
- **LLM/AI to help map / translate / “explain”** metadata fields in different checklists / data infrastructures?
- **Schemas/Checklists to indicate what information need to be present** for data to be used for some particular purpose: can help filtering published data, can help submitters when submitting, and collectors when designing collection logsheets

A selected summary of Day 2

- Culture collections: there are bigger ones and then lab-based smaller ones and they have different issues wrt accessibility to the collection, resources. Making the collections findable, by **adopting common standards may help with harmonisation between collections**; will need to help the smaller ones with this adoption
- **Conversion (or mapping) between standards (incl. taxonomy)** is much more achievable than changing standards used by biobanks for many years.
- Biobanks should use **globally unique identifiers** for samples. This can then be linked by the people that do the bioinformatics analysis. For some organisations this will be a lot of (manual) work!
- To **avoid the loss of historical information**, we need to focus on linking the information (linked open data)
- Dealing with **ABS** and related int'l permits is still a **headache**

A selected summary of Day 2

- General agreement with our vision of **federated libraries guided by shared principles**
- Some countries have/are building their own **national reference libraries**: make sure we use the same (or mapped) standards, conventions, vocabularies, curation principles....
- Not all have the same level of data IT capacity/knowledge: **share share share?**
- **Curation of reference libraries** is (obviously) important but it is not always easy to find out what curation is done. Metadata for this?
- **Confidence levels** are often under-reported. Stricter requirements?
- Annotation databases: **feedback loop** between annotation and sequence databases to inform on annotations that are not good. This applies generally to any DNA-related (meta)data – **when mistakes are found**, what reporting and correcting pathway is there?
- Reference libraries need **long-term support!**

A selected summary of Day 2

- **Publish publish publish:** the reference libraries, the bioinformatics codes. On this: could we be bold enough to state that we vote for tax-paid open and FAIR repositories and not private/commercial ones?

